

Photolysis of Butyl Rubber in Solid State

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The photolysis of butyl rubber films have been investigated with and without diphenylmercury. The data so obtained have been processed to yield the heats of activation for butyl rubber-diphenylmercury system. The importance of production of radicals by diphenylmercury under irradiation conditions have been discussed.

THE polymeric materials deteriorate on exposure to the natural and induced environmental conditions. Among the polymers butyl rubber is of particular interest, since this polymer photodegrades in air at room temperature by ultra-violet radiation. Although kinetics of chain scission of butyl rubber by small amounts of nitrogendioxide has been reported by Jellinek and Coworker¹, no attention has been paid to the photo-degradation and stabilization of butyl rubber in solid state and in the presence of air at the temperatures where thermal degradation is not a significant process.

In the present investigations therefore, the kinetics of photolysis of butyl rubber with diphenylmercury in the temperature range of 265 to 293°K by the light of wavelength 366 nm have been presented. The degradations were followed by light scattering and the kinetic data have been processed to calculate the values of ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔF^\ddagger , the enthalpy, the entropy and the free energy respectively of the activation processes. Quantum yields of photo-oxidative degradation of the rubber with and without incorporation of diphenylmercury have been determined using potassium ferri-oxalate actinometry. We have also determined the optimum concentration of diphenylmercury which would impart saturation photo-stabilization to the rubber in solid state against exposure to 366 nm ultra-violet radiation.

Experimental

The butyl rubber (BR) (a co-polymer of isobutylene and isoprene) (M/s Swastic Rubber Co., Poona) was purified with acetone and methanol extraction and kept in contact with petroleum ether (40-60°). The rubber was precipitated from 1% solution in petroleum ether with acetone. The incorporation of the diphenylmercury (DPM) was effected by dissolving the BR (5%) in cyclohexane containing 0.1, 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0% of DPM on the basis of the weight of the polymer. The BR films

of uniform thickness were prepared by casting 10 ml of the solution in cyclohexane containing BR with and without DPM on quartz plates which were sealed with pyrex glass plates having a 5 cm diameter bore. The films were dried in high vacuum for 24 to 30 hrs to a constant weight.

The photolysis was carried out in air with a 125 watt (230 V) mercury vapour lamp whose glass casing was removed. The dried BR films were irradiated by a monochromatic light of wavelength 366 nm for different intervals of time in the temperature range of 265-293°K.

The intensity of radiation and quantum yields for polymer chain scissions were quantitatively determined by potassium ferri-oxalate actinometry².

The light scattering investigations were made with a light scattering photometer designed and calibrated by the present author³. The photometer is capable of determining absolute turbidities, and weight average molecular weights, within $\pm 1\%$. The refractive index increment with concentration of BR (dn/dc) and the optical constant (H) for the solution in cyclohexane were determined using a Brice-Phoenix differential refractometer (Phoenix Precision Instrument Co., Philadelphia, USA) and the values at 298°K are : $n_o = 1.4338$; $dn/dc = 0.1248$ and $H = 1.957 \times 10^{-6}$.

Absorption measurements were carried out with a Beckman DU Spectrophotometer. The absorption spectra of $6.348 \times 10^{-6} M$ DPM in cyclohexane induced by the different light doses by changing the time of irradiation at 283°K were measured in a quartz cell.

Theoretical : When all the bonds in the polymer chains are broken by random degradation and each bond has equal strength and accessibility,

the following relationship^{4,5} for the zero order reaction can be written :

$$\frac{1}{u_{1(p)}} = \frac{1}{u_{1(o)}} + \frac{m}{wN} \phi I_a t \quad \dots (1)$$

where w is the weight of irradiated polymer, m is the molecular weight of the monomer, N is the Avogadro's number, I_a is the light intensity absorbed in the polymer sample, ϕ is the quantum yield, $u_{1(o)}$ is the initial number average degree of polymerization and $u_{1(p)}$ after degradation. The quantum yield ϕ can be determined from equation (1) by plotting $1/u_{1(p)}$ vs irradiation time t . The ratio $u_{1(p)}/u_{1(o)}$ can be replaced by the ratio of weight average degree of polymerization $u_{2(p)}/u_{2(o)}$ without an appreciable error. These ratios can be conveniently determined by light scattering measurements.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 gives the variation of degree of degradation (p), versus time for BR films irradiated with and without the presence of 0.1% DPM in air at 265°, 273°, 283° and 293°K with the light intensity flux of 1.68×10^{-8} Einstein $\text{sec}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ for different time intervals. An inspection of the plots reveals that at

Fig. 1. Variation of Photo-Degradation Rate of Butyl Rubber in the absence and presence of 0.1% of DPM in air at various temperatures. (Light intensity flux at 366 nm = 1.68×10^{-8} einstein $\text{sec}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$.)

each temperature the values of 'p' of the irradiated samples are greater in absence of DPM as compared to the corresponding values of BR with DPM. This indicates that DPM retards the oxidative degradation of the rubber. For a random chain degradation process, the initial slope of p vs t curve, which should be linear if only one kind of links are ruptured, gives the values of the specific rate constants k_1 . If the plot is non-linear, Jellinek⁶ has indicated the possibility of more than one rate

constants being operative. This method has been used successfully to study the kinetics of degradation of natural rubber⁷, polyethylene⁸ and nitrated Egyptian cotton^{9,10}.

In order to avoid complications arising out of branching at high degrees of degradation, the average values of k_1 were evaluated from the initial slope of (p) vs irradiation time curve (Fig. 1) using the relation¹¹, $p = k_1 t$. The value of the Arrhenius energy of activation ΔE and the frequency factor A have been obtained by using the equation¹².

$$\ln k_1 = \ln A - \Delta E/RT \quad \dots (2)$$

The plots of $\ln k_1$ vs $1/T$ are linear and the values of ' ΔE ' as well as ' A ' can be estimated from the slope and the intercept respectively. Alternatively, one may use the method of least squares to estimate the slopes ($-\Delta E/R$) and the intercepts ($\ln A$) from the data. The data so obtained from the latter method satisfied the equations :

$$k_1 = 9.3 \times 10^{-11} \exp(-777.8/RT) \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ (BR)} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$k_1 = 2.3 \times 10^{-15} \exp(-5350.5/RT) \text{ sec}^{-1} \text{ (BR+0.1\% DPM)} \quad \dots (4)$$

The values of ΔE and A obtained in the absence and presence of DPM are 0.78 kcal mole^{-1} , $9.3 \times 10^{-11} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and 5.4 kcal mole^{-1} , $2.3 \times 10^{-15} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ respectively.

Simha and Wall¹³ have pointed out on theoretical grounds that the first order law is incompatible for an ordinary random chain scission process. Actually this type of degradation obeys zero order reaction with respect to polymer and oxygen concentrations. This has been confirmed by Chandra *et al*¹⁴ for the degradation of the rubber. Recent studies⁴ on the study of degradation process of butyl rubber has further confirmed this point. Thus, it is reasonable to assume that zero order law is obeyed for the degradation of BR and BR+DPM systems investigated.

Assuming the zero order law, it can be shown on the basis of the "Theory of Absolute Reaction Rates"¹² that

$$k_1 = \frac{kT}{h} e^{\Delta S^\ddagger/R} e^{-\Delta H^\ddagger/RT} \quad \dots (5)$$

where k = Boltzmann constant, h = Planck constant,

ΔS^\ddagger = Entropy of activation,

ΔH^\ddagger = Enthalpy of activation for degradation and

$\Delta E = \Delta H^\ddagger$

One can calculate the values of ΔF^\ddagger , the free energy of activation for degradation for the various systems with the help of ΔS^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger at any one specified temperature. In the present case, $T=400^\circ\text{K}$ was chosen for such calculations. Irrespective of the variation in the values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger , the values of ΔF^\ddagger remain almost constant around $44.74 \text{ k cal mole}^{-1}$ in both the cases. This leads to the conclusion that the rate determining step is same for both the systems. The observations emphasise the importance of ΔF^\ddagger for the degradation reactions. It is generally accepted that for a unimolecular reaction, if ΔS^\ddagger is found to be positive, the corresponding activated complex is more probable and the reaction is faster than normal. If ΔS^\ddagger , on the other hand, is negative, the activated complex is less probable. It is observed that in the BR+DPM system, ΔS^\ddagger is more negative and, therefore, the activated complex formed in this case is less probable. For the BR system, where ΔS^\ddagger is less negative the activated complexes formed are more probable.

In the case of BR+DPM system large enthalpy of activation $5.35 \text{ k cal mole}^{-1}$ is compensated by a large negative entropy of activation -130.11 E.U. A large negative entropy and large enthalpy of activation means slow degradation reaction. On the other hand, for BR without DPM system, although $\Delta H^\ddagger 0.78 \text{ k cal mole}^{-1}$, the value of entropy of activation is only -109.02 E.U. Thus, the effect of light is maximum in this case.

It can be seen (Fig. 2) that the quantum yields per chain scissions per absorbed photon decrease with increasing percentage of DPM incorporated in the matrix of BR films at 283°K . The low values of quantum yields for BR+DPM system indicate that

Fig. 2. Effect of concentration of DPM on the ratio of quantum yield of butyl rubber at 283°K .

a polymer with DPM would exhibit high photochemical stability and beyond a concentration of 0.5% DPM incorporated in the matrix of BR

films afforded complete protection from actinic deterioration. The experimental values of quantum yield are in good agreement with the values reported^{1,5} for poly-isoprene, the part of the repeating unit of BR which undergoes photochemical reactions.

The methylenic hydrogen in α -position to the double bond of BR unit is a potential site for hydroperoxidation^{1,6} and the hydroperoxide formed may lead to chain-scission. Any chemical which would induce the decomposition of these intermediates hydroperoxides into non-radical products would contribute to stabilization. The net result of incorporation of DPM is the production of phenyl radicals in the matrix of the polymer film on irradiation. The phenyl radical stabilized by resonance should not react further to initiate new oxidative chains.

From the absorption spectra of irradiated DPM, it was seen that the increase in absorbance is linear with the dose. These experiments indicate that irradiated DPM yields a strongly absorbing radical which acts as an inner filter for UV light. The absorbed light energy may be disposed by internal degradation processes to vibrational energy.

Therefore, it appears that DPM acts via the mechanism of production of free radicals which terminate the chain reaction through radical-radical reaction and by absorbing harmful UV radiation and dissipates the energy as harmless IR radiation or heat.

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